

A Scientometric Study on Bibliotherapy in Scopus Database

DOI: 10.63880/jlii.v1i1.6

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The study aimed to identify and characterize the features of published literature on bibliotherapy from 1942 to 2024. It examined publication year, document type, language, country of origin, institutional contributions, funding bodies, and leading journals to provide a comprehensive understanding of research growth in this field.

Methodology: The Scopus database was selected as the data source, using bibliotherapy as the search term. A total of 1,503 research articles were retrieved and analyzed. Quantitative techniques were applied to measure trends, and Tableau software was used to visualize patterns across time, geography, and institutional contributions.

Findings: The results indicated a steady increase in scholarly output, rising from 3.72 percent in 2013 to 5.72 percent in 2024. The United States was the most productive country with 565 publications. The Karolinska Institute ranked as the leading institution, while the National Institute of Mental Health was identified as the top funding body with 40 supported publications. The Journal of Poetry Therapy, published by Taylor and Francis, emerged as the most active journal, contributing 69 articles.

Implications: The study highlights the value of bibliometric analysis for mapping scholarly activity in bibliotherapy. The findings provide useful insights for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers to

Received: 07.05.2025

Revised: 11.08.2025

Accepted: 16.08.2025

Published: 30.08.2025

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strengthen collaboration, guide future research, and expand the applications of bibliotherapy in both academic and clinical contexts.

Keywords: Mental health, Bibliotherapy, Scientometrics, Citation analysis, Research Productivity, Bibliometric analysis, Bibliometrics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bibliotherapy is a form of therapy that promotes personal development and mental health through books and reading. Its foundation is the notion that reading may be an effective tool for introspection, recovery, and transformation. In a time when mental health consciousness is becoming more and more important, an increasing number of studies demonstrate the transforming power of a lowly but effective tool: reading. Using books and reading to promote mental health and personal development is known as bibliotherapy, and it provides a special and approachable route to self-discovery, healing, and transformation.

With the growth of scholarly communication and digital bibliographic databases, scientometric analysis has become an effective method for assessing research trends and impacts in specialized fields like bibliotherapy. It allows for systematically examining publication output, citation structures, authorship patterns, collaboration networks, and emerging themes, providing valuable insights and identifying future directions.

A central multidisciplinary citation database, Scopus, is essential for mapping global research productivity. Analyzing bibliotherapy publications indexed in Scopus reveals the growth of literature and highlights leading countries, institutions, authors, and journals. Understanding these aspects is crucial for appreciating how bibliotherapy has evolved and its influence on mental health and educational psychology.

This study performs a scientometric analysis of bibliotherapy research in the Scopus database, evaluating growth patterns, collaboration trends, and citation impacts to create a knowledge map and identify future research trajectories.

1.1. Bibliotherapy: What is it?

Bibliotherapy is a therapeutic method that utilises the healing power of reading to enhance mental health, self-awareness, and emotional growth. This method concedes that reading can be a significant catalyst for change, offering a safe environment for individuals to process their emotions, gain different stances on situations, and foster greater empathy.

1.2. Objectives

- The following are the main objectives of this study.
- To identify the world scholarly publication productivity.
- To find out relative growth of literature in the area of bibliotherapy.
- To examine the country-wise distribution.
- To verify top productive institutions.
- To find out top funding bodies producing scholarly publications in the field of bibliotherapy.
- To verify the popular journals in bibliotherapy domain.
- To identify emerging research areas.

- To find out major publication types.
- To know top productive authors.
- To identify top cited article in bibliotherapy domain.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bibliotherapy, the therapeutic use of books and reading materials, has evolved from a supplementary intervention to a structured, evidence-based practice with applications in mental health, education, and crisis response. Early foundational studies, such as Lenkowsky's review in 1987, highlighted its role in special education, while Cohen's work in 1992 explored gender-specific applications in women's mental health. Dow, in 1982, introduced behavioral bibliotherapy, emphasizing self-help methodologies.

Recent research has expanded the scope of bibliotherapy, particularly during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies by Monroy-Fraustro et al. (2021) demonstrated its effectiveness in reducing anxiety and enhancing coping mechanisms. Bibliotherapy has also proven beneficial for children dealing with grief, as noted by Malhi and Bharti (2023), and for improving emotional resilience in school settings, according to Jack and Ronan (2008).

Joseph et al. (2024) conducted bibliometric analyses that reveal a growing interdisciplinary interest, with digital and AI-assisted bibliotherapy emerging as key trends. The role of technology in expanding accessibility, especially for individuals with disabilities, has also been emphasized (Shahbudin & Jamil, 2024). Despite its advantages, challenges remain, including methodological inconsistencies (Eich, 1999), the need for standardized protocols (Redman et al., 2024), and unequal access to digital resources (Eftimova et al., 2022). Future research should prioritise longitudinal studies, cross-cultural adaptations, and AI integration to enhance personalisation and scalability. Bibliotherapy is a versatile and cost-effective intervention with demonstrated efficacy across diverse populations. However, further refinement is needed to maximize its potential in global mental health and educational frameworks.

3. METHODOLOGY

Scopus database was chosen as a representative sample of the population of Bibliotherapy journals. Bibliotherapy is given as a topic in search box of Scopus database. Data was retrieved on 31st of December 2024. The search string used was (TITLE-ABS-KEY (bibliotherapy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (book therapy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (reading therapy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (poetry therapy) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (therapeutic storytelling)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, ar) OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, cp) OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, re) OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, ch) OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, bk)). As a result, 1503 research articles were extracted as .txt file and imported into Excel. From 1942 to 2024 documents has been collected on for examination analysis and visualized in Tableau software. The subsequent methods are used for gathering, analyzing, and interpreting data in order to properly conclude the research problem.

- *Coverage*: The population of the study will be limited to Scopus covered journals from 1942 to 2024.
- *Data Collection*: Data collection was done from the core collection of the Scopus database from 1942 to 2024.
- *Data Analysis*: Data collected shall be scientifically analysed and interpreted using quantitative data analysis software.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1 Scholarly Publications Productivity and Year Wise Growth from 1942-2024

YEAR	Documents	Percentage(n=1503)
2024	86	5.72
2023	78	5.18
2022	67	4.45
2021	61	4.05
2020	56	3.72
2019	57	3.79
2018	65	4.32
2017	68	4.52
2016	56	3.72
2015	66	4.39
1942	1	0.06

Figure 1: Scholarly Publication Productivity and Year Wise Growth in Bibliotherapy

The Figure-1 and Table 1 reflect a growth of publications in the bibliotherapy from 1942 to 2024. In 1942 only 1 document was published, from 1942 to 1980 only 113 articles were published. From 1981 to 2000 total 254 articles were published. In 2013, 3.72% of publications were created, and they increased over time to 5.72% in 2024.

Table 2: Global Trends of Scholarly Publication Productivity in Bibliotherapy

SN	Countries Name	No. of Publications	Publications (%) (n=1503)	Country Ranking
1	United States	565	37.5	1
2	United Kingdom	194	12.9	2
3	Australia	112	7.4	3
4	Canada	89	5.9	4
5	Germany	72	4.7	5
6	Netherlands	53	3.5	6
7	Sweden	37	2.4	7
8	Israel	36	2.3	8
9	China	26	1.7	9
10	Poland	25	1.6	10
11	India	24	1.5	11

Figure 2: Country-Wise Distribution of Publications in Bibliotherapy

The table-2 and figure-2 reflects the top eleven nations generating the most research output in bibliotherapy subject. The United States of America with 37.5% is the top-ranking nation with the most publications. UK stands after with 12.9% among the other nations. Australia is positioned third with 7.4% and Canada stood at the fourth rank with 5.9% and India was in eleventh rank with 1.5% of publications.

Figure 3: Top 10 Most Productive Institutions publishing scholarly communications in the field of Bibliotherapy

The Figure-3 shows the top ten most productive organizations in the area about bibliotherapy. Karolinska Institutet is at the first rank with 1.59% of publications followed by King's College London with 1.53% publications and University of Haifa is ranked third and possesses 1.39% of publications. University of Melbourne generated 1.26% of the articles, Linkopings Universitet held the fifth position with 1.19% of the total publications. The results show that academic institutions and universities situated in the top positions are Sweden and England.

Table 3: Top 10 Funding Bodies

SN	Funding Bodies	No. of Publications	Ranking
1	National Institute of Mental Health	40	1
2	National Institutes of Health	36	2
3	U.S. Department of Health and Human Services	24	3
4	National Health and Medical Research Council	6	4
5	Wellcome Trust	6	5
6	Medical Research Council	5	6
7	National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences	5	7
8	National Natural Science Foundation of China	5	8
9	Vetenskapsrådet	5	9
10	Canadian Institutes of Health Research	4	10

Table-3 shows the top ten funding organizations that provide funding for studies and development in the bibliotherapy. The National Institute of Mental Health is the top funding organization, having provided funding for 40 publications out of a total of 1503 publications. The second-highest funding agency, the National Institutes of Health, has supported 36 (2.39%) publications, followed by U.S. Department of Health and Human Services which stood at the third rank and has funded 24 (1.59%) of publications. National Health and Medical Research Council and Wellcome Trust had funded 6 publications, correspondingly. Additionally, the results show that the primary funding sources were the USA has been leading position when it comes to granting funds across.

Table 4: Popular Journals in the Field of Bibliotherapy as in 2024

S N	Journal Title	Total Publications	Percentage of Publications (n=1503)	Impact Factor
1	<i>Journal of Poetry Therapy</i>	69	4.590	1.3
2	<i>Behaviour Research and Therapy</i>	27	1.796	4.2
3	<i>Journal Of Consulting and Clinical Psychology</i>	25	1.663	4.5
4	<i>Journal Of Clinical Psychology</i>	16	1.064	2.1
5	<i>Journal Of Creativity in Mental Health</i>	15	0.998	0.8
6	<i>Early Child Development and Care</i>	12	0.798	1.4
7	<i>Behavior Therapy</i>	12	0.798	3.7
8	<i>School Psychology International</i>	11	0.731	1.7
9	<i>Behavioural And Cognitive Psychotherapy</i>	11	0.731	2.2
10	<i>Arts In Psychotherapy</i>	10	0.665	1.5

The Table-4 reflects the top ten journals in the field of bibliotherapy from 1942 to 2024. *Journal of Poetry Therapy* published by Taylor and Francis is the top journal during the study period, with an impact factor of 1.3 and 69 publications. Subsequent to the *Behaviour Research and Therapy* published by Elsevier with impact factor 4.2 and 27 publications. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology* published by American Psychological Association with impact factor 4.5 occupies the third position and had 25 publications. *Journal of Clinical Psychology* and *Journal of Creativity in Mental Health* were also among the leading journals with 16 and 15 publications respectively.

Table 5: Emerging Research Area from 1942 to 2024 in the field of Bibliotherapy

SN	Author Name(s)	No. of Publications	Percentage
1	Medicine	886	37.6
2	Psychology	647	27.5
3	Social Sciences	319	13.5

4	Arts and Humanities	148	6.3
5	Nursing	134	5.7
6	Health Professions	52	2.2
7	Neuroscience	42	1.8
8	Computer Science	35	1.5
9	Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology	16	0.7
10	Business, Management and Accounting	15	0.6
11	Others	61	2.6

The Table 5 shows the most popular areas of emerging research from 1942 to 2024, as determined by the quantity of publications. Medicine is the most popular field of study, with 37.6% (886) of publications, followed by Psychology at 27.5% (647). Social Sciences accounts for 13.5% (319), Arts and Humanities for 6.3% (148), and Nursing for 5.8% (134) of publications.

Figure 4: Publication type in the field of Bibliotherapy

Figure-4 represents the top publication type preferred from 1942 to 2024 based on the number of publications. Article with 74% and 1110 documents is the most preferred document type for publication, Review is in second place with 13.4%, Conference review in the last position with 0.1% publications.

Table 6: Most Productive Author in the field of Bibliotherapy

SN	Author Name (s)	No. of Publications	Publications (%) (n=1503)
1	Pardeck, J.T.	21	1.39
2	Andersson, G	15	0.99
3	Cuijpers, P.	15	0.99
4	Scogin, F.	15	0.99
5	Rohde, P.	14	0.93

6	Stice, E.	14	0.93
7	Pehrsson, D.E.	13	0.86
8	Shechtman, Z.	13	0.86
9	Carlbring, P.	12	0.79
10	Williams, C.	12	0.79

Table-6 reflects the topmost productive author in the area of bibliotherapy from 1942 to 2024. Pardeck, J.T. (from Department of Social Work, Southeast Missouri State University, Cape Girardeau, Missouri) with 21 publications leading in first place, Andersson, G (from Linköpings Universitet, Linköping, Sweden), Cuijpers, P. and Scogin, F. with 15 publications is in second to fourth place. Rohde, P. is in fifth place with 14 publications.

Table 7: Top 10 Most Cited articles in Bibliotherapy

SN	Authors	Title	Source title	Total Citations
1	Fiske A.; Wetherell J.L.; Gatz M.	Depression in older adults	<i>Annual Review of Clinical Psychology</i>	1607
2	Cuijpers P.; Donker T.; Van Straten A.; Li J.; Andersson G.	Is guided self-help as effective as face-to-face psychotherapy for depression and anxiety disorders? A systematic review and meta-analysis of comparative outcome studies	<i>Psychological Medicine</i>	663
3	Andrews G.; Basu A.; Cuijpers P.; Craske M.G.; McEvoy P.; English C.L.; Newby J.M.	Computer therapy for the anxiety and depression disorders is effective, acceptable and practical health care: An updated meta-analysis	<i>Journal of Anxiety Disorders</i>	634
4	Rapee R.M.; Schniering C.A.; Hudson J.L.	Anxiety disorders during childhood and adolescence: Origins and treatment	<i>Annual Review of Clinical Psychology</i>	594
5	Ehlers A.; Clark D.M.; Hackmann A.; McManus F.; Fennell M.; Herbert C.; Mayou R.	A randomized controlled trial of cognitive therapy, a self-help booklet, and repeated assessments as early interventions for posttraumatic stress disorder	<i>Archives of General Psychiatry</i>	395
6	Carlbring P, Nilsson-Ihrfelt E, Waara J, Kollenstam C,	Treatment of panic disorder: live therapy	<i>Behaviour Research and Therapy</i>	272

	Buhrman M, Kaldo V, Söderberg M, Ekselius L, Andersson G.	vs. self-help via the Internet.		
7	Miller, W. R., Taylor, C. A., & West, J. C.	Focused versus broad-spectrum behavior therapy for problem drinkers.	<i>Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology</i>	260
8	Cuijpers P.	Bibliotherapy in unipolar depression: a meta-analysis	<i>Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry</i>	257
9	Marrs RW.	A meta-analysis of bibliotherapy studies	<i>American Journal of Community Psychology</i>	256
10	Sagar V. Parikh., et al	Canadian Network for Mood and Anxiety Treatments (CANMAT) 2016 clinical guidelines for the management of adults with major depressive disorder: Section 2. Psychological treatments	<i>Canadian Journal of Psychiatry</i>	252

5. DISCUSSIONS & MAJOR FINDINGS

The study shows from 1942 to 1980 only 113 articles were published. From 1981 to 2000 total 254 articles were published. The output of scholarly publications grew steadily from 3.72% in 2013 to 5.72% in the year 2024. The results indicate that the field of bibliotherapy has expanded over the past ten years. With 565 documents between 1942 and 2024, the United States of America is the top country in the world for scholarly bibliotherapy publications. With 24 publications out of 1503 total, India was ranked eleventh.

Study identifies that with 24 publications in the top-ranking affiliations, the Karolinska Institutet held the top spot, followed by King's College London with 23 publications and University of Haifais ranked third and possesses 21 publications. Because they allocated more funds for research and development, universities and institutions in rich countries wrote more publications than universities and institutions in underdeveloped countries.

The largest funding source is the National Institute of Mental Health, which has provided funding for 40 publications between 2015 and 2024.

The Journal of Poetry Therapy, published by Taylor and Francis, is the leading journal with an impact factor of 1.3 and 69 publications. Behaviour Research and Therapy, as well as the Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, are also among the leading journals.

Medicine is the most popular research area. Psychology is the second most popular emerging research area of study forecasted from the period 2015-2024 in Bibliotherapy. Article is the most popular document type and published 1110 publications with 74%.

6. CONCLUSION

Numerous interpretations of the basic idea of bibliotherapy emerged from the analysis of the retrieved data. When the data was arranged and tabulated, it made it much easier for the researcher to review and evaluate the specifics of the research problem. A completely different understanding of the information that can be deduced from the retrieved data was provided by the graphical representation of each tabulated data set. All of the research objectives were successfully mapped, and the study's inquiries have been adequately addressed. In conclusion, the main goal was to identify the articles published in the field of 'Bibliotherapy' from 1942 to 2024, determine the most productive country in the field, ascertain the language in which most papers on the topic have been published, and compare document formats, languages, countries, etc., among the selected databases.

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